

Teaching English Literature In Iraqi Preparatory Schools After 2013

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Abstract

There is no doubt that early studying of literature develops the process of language learning for both native and foreign speakers. This can be felt easily in almost all fields of language, such as vocabularies, word formation and effective sentences which come to be used as proverbs or slogans, such as 'To be or not to be that is the question' or 'Not all gold that glitters' and so on. Such sentences sometimes encourage learners to look for more, a matter which plays a vital role in developing their language four skills.

This study tries to discuss both advantages and disadvantages of literature focuses in English for Iraq, the curriculum that has been adopted by the Iraqi Ministry of Education since 2013. It also tries to compare (LF) with the (LR), literary works that used to be taught in Iraq before 2013. It also tries to indicate decide (LF) or (LR) are more beneficial or practical.

1. Introduction

This study, which falls into three sections, deals with the literature focus (LF) in Iraqi new curriculum *English for Iraq*. It also casts lights on the *Literary Reader* (LR) which used to be represented by three simplified copies of *Kipps*, *Oliver Twist* and *The Merchant of Venice*. These simplified books used to be taught in Iraqi preparatory schools before 2013.

Section one deals with poetry and particularly with four poems chosen to be studied in book 10 (4th preparatory class). These four poems are Alfred Tennyson's *The Lady of Shallot* and W. B. Yeats's *When You Are Old*. It also deals with two translated-into-English poems which are *Love Song for Words* by Nazik Al-Mala'ika and *Secrets of Fire* by Abdul Wahab Al-Bayyati.

Section two deals with the concept of drama, types of drama and some theatre terms in *English for Iraq* book 11(5th preparatory class). This section presents two elements in *English for Iraq* which are Jawad Al-Assadi's *Hammam Baghdad* and a scene from William Shakespeare's *The Tempest*.

Section three deals with two short stories in book 12 (6th preparatory class). These two short stories are Katharine Mansfield's *The Canary*. The second is Mohammad Khudair's *The Swing*, a story which is translated from Iraqi literature.

A conclusion comes finally to sum up the findings and the recommendation of the study indicating the advantages and the disadvantages of the *Literary Reader* (LR) and literature focus (LF) in *English for Iraq*.

Section i: Poetry

If all literature is good coffee, poetry is an espresso.
(Messieres , 2014, p.106)

Unlike the Arabs who often use lines of poetry in their written or spoken speech, the English people do not have such a tendency. This English tendency seems to be welcome by some writers such as R.T. Jones who expresses his happiness about the idea that there is no regret to lose a large number of poetry terms during the present time. D.H. Laurence supports this idea when he sides with Jones saying that writing prose gives more freedom to writers and speakers and even to typists to divide each paragraph into lines and not restrict themselves to the use of line-endings. (Jones, 1988, p.1).

As far as John Burgess Wilson is concerned, poetry can be considered a dying art for modern readers. Hence, publishers will not risk publishing a lot of verse books for sales will not bring much profits and this will be an economic loss. Wilson adds that this eras a novel era. A matter which is supported by the future internationalization of English literature which is longer limited to be read in English speaking countries but has become a world phenomenon (Wilson, 1969, p.294). Wilson seems to support the idea that internationalization

of English will strengthen prose books such as novels and short stories which are preferable by non-native readers who face difficulty in understanding poetry.

In spite of this diminishing interest in reading poetry, the role of poetry in developing language for both foreign English learners and native speakers cannot be denied. Therefore, methods of teaching poetry have been developed in literature classes. The aim of developing these methods is to increase the students' interest in reading poetry. These methods also aim at dealing with the clear decline in interest in students who prefer hearing poetry to reading it, a reading which requires more efforts particularly concerning its special skill whether in rhymes or meters. (Nica, 2011, p.1). Some language learners – when asked by the researcher – reason out this poetry abandonment by the idea that poetic texts have no place in their daily activities. Some critics declare that this worrying phenomenon urges us not to complain but to find a solution, such as looking for literature which is funny and interesting and easy to understand by the majority of learners.

The NIC has an advantage concerning this problem. Unlike the OIC – which neglects teaching poetry – the NIC presents some interesting and easy-to-understand poems. A matter which encourages some students not only to read these poems but also to watch and hear them sung on the YouTube. The author of *English for Iraq: 4th Preparatory* Caroline de Messieres – before selecting some poems in the books – gives some literary opinions to convince the students about the linguistic value of poetry. She adds that people who read fictions and poetry are better at understanding other people. (Messieres, 2014, p.107).

Messieres is of the idea that reading poems takes us out of ourselves and makes us look beyond the limits that restrict our way of thinking, and this can be a way to bring pleasure and joy. She also familiarizes the students with the definitions of some important poetic terms such as image, metaphor and personification. In addition to that, she presents a general description of the types of poetic forms, such as sonnet, lyric and epic and free verse. She not only defines these terms but tries to develop the students' poetic taste and ability by asking them to find out these poetic terms in the poems and ask them – to some extent – to analyze the poetic texts. (Messieres, 2014, p.107)

The two English chosen poems to be taught in *English for Iraq: 4th Preparatory* are really well-chosen to represent two glorious eras of English literature: the Victorian and the twentieth century era. The first poem is *The Lady of Shalott* by Alfred Tennyson (1809-1892). This poem – which deals with the legend of Arthur – is considered a prelude to Tennyson's famous masterpiece *Idylls of the King* (Sen, 2010, p.126). Selecting this poem for the students of this age has several advantages. First, it mixes the theme of love with the concepts of nature. Hence, it enriches the students' language mentality by introducing highly effective literary expressions, and it also evokes the students' imaginative ability for the fact that it starts with the description of green nature.

On either side the river lie
Long fields of barley and of rye,
That clothe the wold and meet the sky;
And thro' the field the road runs by
To many-tower'd Camelot;
And up and down the people go,
Gazing where the lilies blow

Caroline de Messieres – in spite of the simple language the poet starts the poem with – tries to familiarize the students with the new nature and plant words used in its first part such as *barley*, *rye* and *lily*. She also emphasizes words which are of high poetic effect such as *clothe* and *wold* (Messieres, 2014, p.107). Another educational merit of this poem is its easily-read structure which is divided into four parts in an interesting narrative way. This structure or division makes it one of the most beautiful and most interesting narrative poem in the English language, a poem which expresses an educational lesson for it reflects a moral lesson dealing with the risks and inadequacy of an isolated life (Tilak, 2009, p.113).

The poem is divided into four parts with stanzas in each part. Its language – which has the simplicity of the medieval ballad-makers with continuous repetitions – is highly musical. Music is expressed through some devices, such as the " the alliteration in *Four gray walls, and four gray towers*, and in *only reapers, reaping early*. There is also artistic use of medial rhymes as in *Long fields of barley, and of rye*, or in *Chanted loudly, chanted lowly* on the whole Tennyson's rhyming in this poem is highly powerful and justifies the praise of the critic who writes that in this poem Tennyson's music looks like a ghost which haunts all the lines (Tilak, 2009, p.112).

The division of the this poem into parts and then into stanza makes it easy to study. In each part, there is an idea which is clarified in detail in the stanzas. The first part gives a background of the story of a mysterious lady who lives alone unseen by others. In the second part a mysterious voice attacks her ear. This voice warns her not to look outside, otherwise she would be cursed to death. The magic of love is clarified in part three when the lady is stunned when her mirror reflects a picture of a knight, a reflection which causes her end. So, the reader – in the last part – is not surprised to know her end or her death because he has already been informed about all her details in a narrative musical style (Tilak, 2009, p.117).

The second English chosen poet in *English for Iraq: 4th Preparatory* is W. B. Yeats (1865-1939). Choosing this poet by the author is also a successful task firstly because there is some sort of style similarity and approximation between Yeats and Alfred Tennyson for the idea that Yeats – like Tennyson – starts his poetic career as a poet of fantasy and legend. Second, his poetic language is so direct and rich that every diction in his poem is full of meaning; his musical style is so simple that it is framed by the rhythms of everyday speech. The repetition of his image makes the theme of his poem simple and plain (Wollman, 1972, p.147).

Yeats' chosen poem in *English for Iraq: 4th Preparatory* is *When You Are Old*. Love is the main theme in this poem which – like *The Lady of Shallot* – talks about a lady loved by a poet who will finally be deprived of her. In addition to this theme which is preferable by the students of this age, Yeats's style enriches the theme by repeating the word 'loved' four times in the second stanza.

So, putting this poem after *The Lady of Shallot* in *English for Iraq: 4th Preparatory* is of several advantages because the students have been already prepared to repeat almost the same love words and discuss the same theme, a theme of loving a lady who – to some extent – does not care about a lover who is moaning for her. Another advantage for introducing Yeats to Arab students is that he carefully observed the high esteem the Arabs allocate for literature in general and poetry in particular. Furthermore, he tries to link between the old poetry in Arabia and that in Ireland and draws a conclusion that these two types of poetry have many things in common. (AlZuhairi, 2018, p.8).

The other two chosen poems in *English for Iraq: 4th Preparatory* are not English; rather they are translated from Arabic literature. These two poems are *Love Song for Words* by Nazik Al-Mala'ika (1923-2007), and *Secrets of Fire* by Abdul Wahab Al-Bayyati (1926-1999). Nevertheless, these two poems enrich the students with literary synonyms, such as *fragrant* and *perfumed*, *heartening* and *encouraging*. Also, these two poems introduce the students to a very important term in literature which is the free verse, a verse whose main pillars are Nazik Al-Mala'ika and Abdul Wahab Al-Bayyati (Messieres, 2014, p.107).

Al-Bayyati's main theme in *Secrets of Fire* can be linked with these in *When You Are Old* and *The Lady of Shallot*. In all these poems there is a poet who is singing for a lady and pleads her not to disappoint him. Al-Bayyati starts his poem describing a man who – on the last day – kisses the hands, the lips and even the eyes of his lady describing her as an apple to eat. In spite of this theme which makes this poem lovable for the students, it seems that teaching translated poetry for students in this age is not of a high linguistic fruit, because they are in urgent need to learn English literature from native poets or native speakers, and also because rhythms and rhymes are lost in translating poetry.

Section ii: Drama

Since plays are written for performance they are different in nature from novels or poetry. (Kelsall, 1989, p.1)

The OIC gives a wide field to drama by presenting a complete simplified copy of William Shakespeare's *The Merchant of Venice*. In spite of this, the OIC does not have the advantage the NIC has which is the short introduction to drama and theatre terms. The author of *English for Iraq: 5th Preparatory* Olivia Johnston – before presenting extracts from two plays – introduces the students to what the word drama means, clarifying the types of drama; comedy and tragedy and listing the definitions of some important theatre terms, such as director, actors and audience. Knowing such terms, the students start reading the plays with a bit of previous information about this field of knowledge. (Johnston, 2014, p.116).

In *English for Iraq: 5th Preparatory*, there are two extracts from two famous plays. The first is an extract from William Shakespeare's *The Tempest* (1610), a fable which is full of ambiguous meaning. It was probably the last play that Shakespeare wrote and can be considered his farewell to the theatre. The play can also be read as a political lesson in which the evil forces of power will look at themselves differently and re-establish some false concepts. There is also a personification of the human psyche in the this play. (Patterson, 2005, p.403).

Despite the fact that this play is a comedy, this does not necessarily mean that it is funny. It talks about a wise and learned duke named Prospero. Because Prospero spends his time reading books, he lets his younger brother Antonio rule the country for him. Antonio makes a plan with the King of Naples to get rid of Prospero. The King of Naples orders Gonzalo to kill Prospero. Gonzalo, a kind man, leaves Prospero in a boat with food and books. Miranda, Prospero's daughter, is pleasing her father in the boat until they arrive at an island where they meet a fairy called Ariel who could change himself so that no one except Prospero could see him.

One day, Prospero – with the magic he learns from books – causes a big storm to bring the ship of Antonio, Gonzalo, the King of Naples, his brother Sebastian and his son Ferdinand to the island. Magically, Prospero isolates Ferdinand from his father. Then Ferdinand falls in love with Miranda and marries her. On the other part of the island, the King of Naples is looking for his son, Ferdinand.

On the island, Antonio convinces Sebastian to kill the king. They try to do so, but the spirit Ariel appears with his wings and prevent them. Then, Ariel reminds Antonio with his old crime, the attempt to kill Prospero. Finally, Prospero gathers them all, reminding them to what they did to him. He forgives them all and brings back Ferdinand to his father who is shocked to see Ferdinand and Miranda. Finally, Prospero gets back his throne and becomes a duke a gain. (Paul, 2010p.29)

Hence – and despite the fact that this imaginary play looks like a cartoon with the supernatural elements it has - it has many moral lessons which makes it suitable to the students in this age. The most prominent feature of this story is the supernatural atmosphere which almost dominates its events from the beginning to the end. Nevertheless, Shakespeare does not make human characters absent in these events; rather real actors are everywhere in all the scenes. Doing so, Shakespeare touches upon the idea that even supernatural powers sympathize with the mistakes committed by human (Paul, 2010 p.59). This may lead to an idea that choosing this play for students are of a very important moral lesson which is forgiveness may be possible even to those who try to commit big crimes; this forgiveness is sometime enough to send them back to their humanity.

The second drama in *English for Iraq: 5th Preparatory* is a translated extract from an Iraqi play which is Jawad Al-Assadi's *Baghdadi Bath*. Al-Assadi (1947 -) is one of the most famous contemporary Iraqi dramatists who spends twenty five years as an expatriate. Most of his works are translated into English, Russian and French. *Baghdadi Bath* is a play about two Iraqi brothers. These two brothers work as bus drivers between Baghdad and Syria after 2003, a very dangerous period on this land route for both drivers and passengers. The brothers Majeed, the elder, supports the Americans while Hameed hates them. (Johnston, 2014, p.116). This play can be a historic document to the students who should know much about a very important period in the history of Iraq.

Being summarized, both *The Tempest* and *Baghdadi Bath* cannot give the students the full meaning of what a play means. *The Tempest*, for instance, is a long play in which there are many lessons such as faith and deception, lessons which are lost when it is summarized.

Section iii: Short Story

The desire to listen to stories appears to be as deeply rooted in the human animal as the sense of property. From the beginning of history, men have gathered round the camp fire, or in a group in the market place, to listen to the telling of a story. (Deedari , 2008, p.1)

If critics are really different about how to describe a literary genre, they are different about short story. Although short story may be a page or two pages, it can be a hundred pages, such as D. H. Lawrence's *St Mawr*. That is why it is sometimes impossible to differentiate between long short story and short novel, a matter which motivates some critics to use the term *novella* for these doubtful examples. The only base on which readers can depend in deciding whether or not this literary work is a short story is its definition. A short story should be a simple thing; it aims at producing one clear event which must grow rapidly and finish before a reader gets tired. (Deedari , 2008, p.1)

Writing a short story requires a high skill. As soon as you start writing a short story, hundreds of ideas may attack your mind. So, it is the writer's creativity which determines the best of these ideas and present them through the actions and speech of fictional characters which seem real to the reader, actions which should be introduced compactly rejecting all unnecessary details. (Deedari, 2008, p.1).

Unlike the OIC which has no place for short story, The NIC presents this literary genre to the students in *English for Iraq: 6th Preparatory*, which is book 12 or the last book in *English for Iraq*. It is a pity that this book does not provide the students with an introduction about short story, a matter which has been done well in *4th Preparatory* and *5th Preparatory* when the authors emphasize poetry and drama.

The author, Olivia Johnston, selects two famous short stories to be studied by students in this year which qualifies them to their university study. The first is a translated excerpt from *The Swing* Mohammed Khudhair (1942 -). Like Jawad Al-Assadi's works, Khudhair's short stories are translated into English, Russian and French.

Choosing *The Swing* in this year has high moral lessons. This story can be described as a condemnation of war wherever it happens; it fills the students' minds with war-hatred and peace-love. Also, it supports the family life and the faithful relationships among friends. It stresses the idea that war destroys everything. Furthermore, it does not only end the lives of some people and send them to graves but also ends the hope of those who survive. *The Swing* talks about an Iraqi faithful soldier who has just come back from 1967 war. He finds it difficult to tell the family of his friend that he was killed in the battles. Then, he tries to convince the four year child Haleema, his friend's daughter that her father now looks like smoke and she can see him only when she closes her eyes. (Johnston, 2015, p.87).

In addition to the moral lesson *The Swing* teaches, it – like Jawad Al-Assadi's *Baghdadi Bath English for Iraq: 5th Preparatory* – can be taken as a historic document about a very essential war the Iraqi Army had in 1967, a war which changed all the events in the second half of the twentieth century, a war which represented a turning point for actions the students should know in their future.

The second short story in *English for Iraq: 6th Preparatory* is *The Canary* by Katherine Mansfield (1888-1923). *The Canary* talks about an old woman suffering from loneliness. This woman buys a canary in a tiny cage. The woman expresses how she and the canary shares each other's life in a way that their relationship has become perfect company. The woman indicates that the canary, unlike the three young men who live with her in her house, understands her way of life and shows this understanding with a type of wonderful singing which is – as the woman says – different from the singing of all other canaries. Finally, the woman finds the canary dead in a miserable way in the cage, a matter which motivates the woman not to have any other bird or even a pet. (Johnston, 2015, p.87).

Choosing a work written by Katherine Mansfield is of high literary importance because she is one of the most three or four remarkable short story writers in the twentieth century. Being open to different interpretations, *The Canary* is of a special importance because it evokes the students' creativity. It can be taken as a love short story, love which is not necessarily boy-girl love. Or, it can be taken as a symbolic love story for readers who know Katherine's biography and know the story of her younger brother's death. The most important in Katherine Mansfield's is the death of her younger brother who was killed in 1915. Perhaps, he was the person she loved most. His sorrowful end takes her mind back and makes her write about her past with a noticeable nostalgia. This longing inspired her to write some short stories. (Deedari, 2008, p.23).

The only disadvantage concerning choosing *The Canary English for Iraq: 6th Preparatory* is not about the story itself, but because it is summarized. According to R.J. Rees whose opinion was quoted in *Understanding Short Story*, summarizing the plots of Katherine's short stories is not fruitful because plot is their important element. She skillfully develops some small events of everyday life. She is a writer who gives much attention to details such as the influence of light on the branches of tree, the colour of flowers, or even the way how a bird sings or moves the swings and the claws. (Deedari, 2008, p.23).

All in all, teaching short story in Iraqi preparatory is a strength point which can be added to the series *English for Iraq*. This genre may motivate the students to read more short stories and may be able to write or even become short-story writers in the future.

Conclusion

Since literature can be briefly defined as ' language well used ', reading literary works are an aim for all those who want to speak well. Fortunately – with advantages and disadvantages– Iraqi curriculum has been presenting English literary works for more than forty years. In 1979, *Kipps*, *Oliver* and *The Merchant of Venice* were simplified well to be taught in Iraqi preparatory schools in a series which was called Literary Reader (LR). After 2013, (LR) was replaced by Literature Focus (LF). This study comes up with a short comparison between (LR) and (LF) and tries to show the advantages and disadvantages for both.

One admirable advantage of (LF) is that it introduces the students to two English literary genres: poetry and short story. This new experiment has been touched by the researcher who has been teaching English in Iraqi Preparatory schools since 1999, which means teaching English literature in (OIC) and (NIC). After 2013, many students began to love looking for more short stories and poems.

As far as (OIC) is concerned, there are merits which (NIC) lacks. First, (LR) includes teaching novel, a genre which is neglected in (NIC). Second, (OIC) does not present literary works as extracts or excerpts which

sometimes spoil the main idea or plots, rather it presents famous complete novels and plays in a simplified way. Third, testing in (NIC) adopts short questions, such as (What is Katherine Mansfield? Or and are two short stories written by Mohammed Khudair). These questions, which can be answered by few words, do not develop the students' writing skill. The (OIC) testing in the essay form plays a vital role in enriching the linguistic mentality, especially in word formation which the students learn spontaneously in sentences like ' Antonio was *kind* and *generous* his *kindness* and *generosity* made him loved by others'

The recommendation that this study may come up with is that there should be a mixture in advantages of both (OIC) and (NIC). This can be done through some well-studied programmed. First, students should be introduced to all literary genres, such as studying short story and poetry in the fourth preparatory, drama in the fifth and novel in the sixth. Second, these literary works should be taught completely as it was adopted in (LR). Third, prose work should be simplified because their advanced language is difficult for preparatory students.

Finally, taking benefit from both (LF) and (LR) will provide students will support students with a developed polished English they cannot get in reading newspapers or reading online. Such a careful study will not only develop their English as speakers who need it as a widespread language, but also may motivate some of them to be writers especially in the field of short story.

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